

PACIFICUS

A Literary Magazine (Print & e-Publication)

Volume I, Issue I | A Quarterly Publication

ISSN (Online): 3082-4079 | ISSN (Print): 3082-4060

Publisher: Binas Publishing

Email: binasbookers2013@gmail.com

DR. NOVA NESS FABRIENNE CARIN

Assistant Professor III

Negros Oriental State University-Main Campus I

Novaness.carin@norsu.edu.ph

“ENGLISH BEYOND BORDERS”

The peregrination of the English language across the globe is striking. Although it experienced a decline sometime in the 19th century, it still survived as a language spoken in the corridors of politics, business, academia, and many others in the modern era. Even today, few people know about its roots, its spread, and its global status. However, unlike any other language, English never fades to repeat its history. Thus, it is still significant to explore the diffusion of the English language particularly on the emergence of its varieties in the global scene, its pragmatic uses in the global arena, and its distinction as a second language in innumerable territories.

The diffusion of the English language brings out its diverging varieties. English is spoken today on all five continents as a result of colonial expansion in the last centuries. Without a doubt, colonization marked the beginning of the spread of the English language. Although American English is extremely influential because it highly dominates the world of politics, showbiz, trade and technology, popular music, and the internet, there are still other varieties of English that are essential tools for human communication (History of English Language, n.d). Trudgill (2000) mentions the World Englishes, which include Australian English, New Zealand English, Canadian English, South African English, Indian English, Caribbean English, Philippine English, and many others. Each of these varieties has its linguistic characteristics. For instance, Philippine English is one of the varieties which has been extremely used in all sectors of society. Dayag (2012) notes that Philippine English “shares some of the linguistic properties ascribed to other varieties of English, especially those used in Asia, which has features that are unique to it.” Not only does Philippine English has its unique linguistic features, but some other varieties, such as Indian English, also feature its pronunciation and vocabulary. Each of these varieties has its function, which in turn is comprehensible and appropriate for such a sociolinguistic context.

Since English plays a crucial role in the field of communication globally, it also creates a sense of bilingualism or even multilingualism in other territories, taking into account that it is sometimes considered a second language by them. In the Philippine context, bilingualism is very evident, considering that it is composed of many islands and many people who speak different languages. Nevertheless, people who belong to different cultures and who speak different languages can communicate the said language using their linguistic styles. According to Espinosa (1997), “English is not an alien tongue. Filipino children may not understand the nuances of the English language, but they can manipulate it. English is familiar and even user-friendly.” This simply implies that no matter what the national language is being used, English is still part of every conversation. Thus, other terms would emerge that is, code switching or code mixing. These are very relevant in the Philippine context, particularly in the academic setting. Each speaker would have his or her code

depending on the context. Sometimes, code-switching could be one of a “linguistic play” according to Bautista (2004) to somehow “achieve a humorous effect by playing the Tagalog or English word.”

Other than having a special feature for the non-native varieties, it also creates speech communities. More often than not, a nonnative variety would create speech communities in different contexts so as to achieve a comprehensible output –successful communication among various speakers with different cultural and social backgrounds. However, it is not just all about understanding these terms but it is about making “all kind of spontaneous adjustments to your pronunciation, vocabulary, grammar, and level of formality so that your speech or writing is appropriate to the context, or at least appropriate as you want it to be” (Davies, 2005).

Although varieties of the English language emerged, it is undeniable that it has pragmatic uses in the global arena. Despite its nuances, the English language remains to be a user-friendly language. It has great significance in all various sectors of society since it is the leading language of science, technology, business, education, popular music, and international negotiations. There are several reasons why English is a very valuable language to learn. In the first place, it is internationally known. Two people who come from different countries such as America and India can communicate through the use of the said language because of its being common. It is a much more important language to get connected with the international level. Thus, there is no reason why it should be avoided.

The English language is also very relevant in the digital age. In this present day, it has become a popular and very useful language in all means of communication including the internet and social media. For instance, it is the best way to get access to a great amount of information on the internet today. Korpela (2003) mentions that “in general, the universal language on the Internet is English, or more exactly a vague collection of languages called ‘English’ because their common origin is the national language spoken in England by the English.” That national language has spread over the world, and several variants such as American (US) English, Australian English, etc. exist. A great number of people whose native language is none of the variants know English as a foreign language. They typically use a more or less simplified variant, e.g., excluding most of the idioms of British, American, Australian, etc. English. Of course, they make mistakes, and sometimes, the ‘English’ used by people as a foreign language on the Internet is almost incomprehensible to anyone else.

Not only English is important in the world of technology but in education as well. These days, it is imperative to learn English, especially among non-native speakers of the language. It is even deemed to be a global phenomenon to learn the language despite its complexities (Martin, 2008). It is evident in the Philippine context that students from other countries tend to converge in the country to enroll in some English programs or even get hold of their chosen degrees, considering that it is best known to offer such English courses. For instance, students from Korea, Tibet, China, and other countries that consider English as a foreign language simply try their best to learn the language with the help of teachers or friends who have a command of the language. This somehow leads to another important reason why English is so important, which is that it brings job opportunities since it is being used in the business industry. It is even a dominant business language and has become almost a necessity for people to speak English if they are to enter a global workforce. Sometimes, English has become a passport to land a job. Moreover, companies require applicants to be competent and skillful but that does not end there. One cannot simply be interviewed without a command of language since most companies assess the communication skills of the applicants through processes such as interviews and the writing of compositions. For instance, Davies (2005) notes the power of English as a tool of communication in the field of call centers. She says that the rapid increase of the call center industry across the globe somehow creates job opportunities. This is worth noting since customer service

representatives could not just utter any language except English that is globally comprehensible and intelligible. Although English embraces a lot of varieties with linguistic characteristics, still it is generally accepted and used by the speakers just to achieve the desired outcome – successful communication between the sender and the receiver.

The distinction of English as a second language in innumerable territories is a hallmark of its prestige in the global sphere. Seemingly, the English language is a remnant of colonial domination. Nearly two billion people speak English as a non-native language. More often than not, these non-native speakers speak the language for some reason. First, their territories were colonized by the native speakers. Second, it is the language used globally. And third, there is no other language that could be somehow understood by different people coming from various countries except English. For one, British authorities were successful in expanding their language since it brought about a great impact on the lives of the people. People these days can communicate using the language despite its intricacies. Also, it has become a language among educated people to connect with the rest of the world using technology including the Internet and social media. In the same manner, through the English language, understanding a diverse culture has become a gradual spectacle.

English as a second language is a tool to get ahead in the world. It has become increasingly more important to inter-global communication. However, as a common language, it does not mean everyone speaks it the same way. Teachers have to play the role of teachers that help the students to use the form of English most suitable for their contexts as well as expose them to linguistic features and cultural styles for them to discern meaning even when the words, grammar, and pronunciation are different from English they are being taught to speak. In other words, the ultimate goal is to achieve communicative competence and sociolinguistic competence. Being an immensely varied language, it attracts people because of its wealth in terms of vocabulary and prestige. Besides, with the emergence of its non-native varieties, substantial uses, and eminence as a second language, it still has great significance and influence.

REFERENCES

- Bautista, M.L. (2004). Tagalog-English code-switching as a mode of discourse. Retrieved from <http://files.eric.ed.gov/fulltext/EJ720543.pdf>
- Dayag, D. (2012). *English in Southeast Asia: Features, policy and language in use*. Retrieved from Benjamins.com
- Davies, D. (2005). *Varieties of modern English*. Great Britain: Pearson Education limited.
- Espinosa, D. (1997). English in the Philippines. Retrieved from <http://gilesig.org/26Phil.htm>
- Korpela, J. (2003). English-the universal language on the internet? Retrieved from <https://www.cs.tut.fi/~jkorpela/lingua-franca.html>
- Martin, R. (2008). English as a medium of instruction in the Philippines. Retrieved from <https://www.ue.edu.ph/manila/uetoday/index.php?nav=27.htm&archive=200808>

History of English Language (n.d.). Retrieved March 31, 2016, from <https://www.englishclub.com/English-language-history.htm>

